

Right-Sizing Complexity: Empirical Limits of Hypergraph Community Detection in Recommenders

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Community detection is often proposed to improve recommender systems by modeling higher-order relations. We test this claim on a proprietary video-on-demand platform and the MovieLens-1M benchmark using implicit feedback and content metadata. User–item–context data are modeled as hypergraphs with Louvain-style modularity and as item–item graphs with modularity-based communities, then compared to collaborative, content-based, and hybrid CF+CBF baselines. Across top-k ranking metrics (Recall@K, nDCG@K), community-aware models yield at best modest gains over a simple content-based model and often fail to beat a strong item–item collaborative filter, despite higher modularity. Analyses point to over-segmentation of sparse interactions and noise from heuristic higher-order relations. A conventional CF+CBF hybrid matches or surpasses community-aware variants in accuracy and efficiency, suggesting that added graph or hypergraph complexity is rarely justified under these data conditions.

Keywords: Recommender systems; Hypergraphs; Community detection; Louvain; Modularity.

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1. Introduction

Community detection is a cornerstone of network analysis, used to reveal groups of nodes with dense intra-group interactions and sparser inter-group ties, and is often invoked to improve recommender systems by injecting higher-order relational structures into the learning signal [1,2]. On social and media platforms, communities are presumed to capture shared interests that can be exploited for personalization. However, most deployed recommenders still rely on pairwise interaction graphs (e.g., user–item edges), which only partially reflect the multiway associations present in real-world systems.

Hypergraphs generalize graphs by allowing hyperedges to connect multiple vertices simultaneously, offering a natural way to encode interactions among users, items, and contextual attributes, such as tags or categories [3–5]. This representation promises to preserve multiway dependencies that are otherwise lost when reducing data to pairwise edges. The Louvain algorithm, a widely used heuristic for modularity maximization in graphs, has therefore been adapted to hypergraph settings to detect communities that reflect such higher-order structures [6–8]. However, two challenges persist: (i) modularity is not uniquely defined for hypergraphs, and its practical surrogates vary in bias and sensitivity to sparsity; and (ii) node moves affect all incident hyperedges, complicating optimization and often encouraging over-segmentation when interactions are thin.

Similar small-world and scale-free signatures have been observed in biological higher-order networks. For example, RNA variation networks over the space of RNA shapes exhibit heavy-tailed degree distributions and short characteristic path lengths, underscoring how higher-order encodings can alter community structure and navigability [9]. More broadly, when community detection objectives are intractable or ill-posed, domain-specific heuristics, as in haplotype reconstruction where clustering under MEC/MEC/GI models is used to recover latent structure, are common and often necessary [11].

This study offers an empirical reassessment of hypergraph community detection for real-world video-on-demand (VOD) platform recommendations. Using implicit feedback (watch time, views, likes/dislikes) and content metadata (genres, characters/tags), we construct both user and item hypergraphs and then derive communities with h-Louvain (a Louvain-style procedure that optimizes a hypergraph modularity objective and stabilizes early iterations). We then evaluate the resulting community-aware scoring against strong collaborative and content-aware baselines.

Across standard top-k ranking metrics, hypergraph communities yield at best marginal and frequently non-significant gains. Moreover, a conventional hybrid of content-based and collaborative filtering outperforms the hypergraph variants in terms of both accuracy (Recall@K) and efficiency (runtime/throughput). Component-wise analyses indicate two main factors: (i) over-segmentation of already sparse interactions, which limits cross-community generalization, and (ii) amplification of sparsity- and noise-related effects in the induced higher-order structure. The pattern mirrors results from microarray cancer classification, where careful feature selection via meta-heuristics (e.g., Grey Wolf Optimizer) paired with deep models can outperform more complex structural encodings if the latter amplifies sparsity/noise rather than signal [10].

2. Higher-Order Communities and Recommenders

2.1. Community Detection in Networks

Classical community detection aims to identify groups of nodes that are more densely connected internally than externally, and has become a core tool in social network analysis, biology, and recommender systems. Beyond purely structural formulations, recent surveys emphasize that modern methods increasingly exploit both interaction structure and node/edge attributes. For example, content- and interaction-aware approaches explicitly model user features, item attributes, and edge semantics to uncover communities whose members share both similar connectivity patterns and similar profiles [12]. These methods are commonly organized into three families—node content-based, edge content-based, and joint node–edge content-based approaches—reflecting whether attribute information is attached primarily to vertices, links, or both. Such attribute-enriched communities are especially attractive for downstream tasks like targeted marketing, anomaly detection, and recommendation, where homophily in both behavior and features is desirable.

At the same time, the computational complexity of community detection remains a central concern for large-scale, dynamic platforms. A broad line of work has catalogued hierarchical clustering algorithms (agglomerative and divisive) for community detection and analyzed their asymptotic and practical costs [13]. This literature highlights the trade-off between expressive community structure (e.g., overlapping or hierarchical communities) and the feasibility of deploying these methods on massive, evolving graphs typical of real-world systems. In particular, many hierarchical algorithms incur super-linear or even higher complexity, motivating the adoption of faster heuristics (such as Louvain-style methods) and careful engineering when community detection is used inside latency-sensitive pipelines like recommender systems. Our study situates hypergraph community detection within this broader landscape, asking whether the added structural richness justifies its computational overhead compared to strong, simpler baselines.

2.2. Hypergraph Modularity: What Louvain is

The Louvain method is a fast, greedy heuristic that optimizes graph modularity by iterating two phases: (i) local node moves that maximize the modularity gain and (ii) aggregation of discovered communities into super-nodes, repeating until convergence. Its appeal is its speed and good partitions at the scale. h-Louvain adapted Louvain’s greedy modularity maximization to hypergraphs by optimizing a hypergraph modularity objective, qH [6]. Because early nodes move on sparse, high-order edges can stall (“lift-off” issue), h-Louvain warms up with a blended objective that linearly combines the graph modularity of the 2-section (clique expansion) with the target hypergraph modularity, gradually shifting the weight to qH . The blend schedule is governed by two parameters and is tuned using Bayesian optimization. This preserves higher-order structures while avoiding the early degeneracies that occur if one naïvely runs Louvain against qH from scratch.

Let $G_2(H)$ be the 2-section of hypergraph H . h-Louvain maximizes

$$Q_\alpha = \alpha qH + (1 - \alpha) Q(G_2(H)), \quad \alpha \in [0,1] \quad (1)$$

where qH is a hypergraph modularity (e.g., the τ -modularity family, with strict variants determining how an edge contributes based on its within-community majority), and $Q(\cdot)$ is standard graph modularity on the 2-section.

Given a user–item hypergraph H , h-Louvain maximizes a blended objective (Equation 1) starting with small α to “lift off” using the 2-section graph $G_2(H)$ and gradually increasing $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ so the final partition is driven by hypergraph modularity qH . Optimization proceeds exactly like Louvain: repeated local node moves that greedily maximize ΔQ_α , followed by aggregation of communities into super-nodes, iterating until no further gain. The α schedule (two parameters) is tuned via Bayesian optimization to avoid poor regions of the search space. In practice, caching incident-hyperedge counts keeps runtime near Louvain’s while adding overhead only from evaluating qH and the tuning loop.

h-Louvain helps when higher-order edges (user–user, item–item) are dense and reliable, so the majority contributions reflect genuine communities. It doesn’t help when interactions are sparse, tags are noisy, or edges are heuristic rather than observed — in those cases strong hybrid baselines (content + CF) usually win on both Recall@K and throughput, as we observe in our VOD setting. For the graph side, Leiden outperforms Louvain in terms of speed.

2.3. *Hypergraph Modularity: Leiden*

Leiden refines Louvain’s local-move phase to ensure well-connected communities and avoid Louvain’s known failure mode of yielding disconnected communities after aggregation. Empirically, Leiden is typically faster (approximately 2–20× in the first iterations on large networks) and finds higher-quality partitions while providing explicit connectivity guarantees. Although defined for graphs and modularity, these advantages motivate preference for Leiden-style local moves when feasible in higher-order settings.

2.4. *Recommender Systems Primer*

Recommender methods fall, broadly, into collaborative, content-based, and hybrid families. Collaborative filtering (CF) learns directly from user–item interactions. In its memory-based form, item–item (or user–user) similarity models compute neighbors over the interaction matrix and are prized for robustness and production simplicity; item-based CF remains a strong baseline at scale. Model-based CF factors the interaction signal into latent representations; in implicit-feedback settings (watch time, views, likes), confidence-weighted matrix factorization was introduced to handle graded “confidence” rather than explicit ratings.

Content-based recommenders, in contrast, use item/user features (such as genres, characters, and embeddings) to score relevance and mitigate cold-start. Similar to most modern large-scale systems, hybrid designs combining these signals (feature-rich MF, two-tower candidates plus learned ranking) often deliver the best trade-off between accuracy and robustness; industrial systems such as YouTube and Meta exemplify such two-stage hybrids. Along this line, hybridization can occur not only between content and CF, but also

between CF and additional side information: social relationships and communities have been used to alleviate cold-start and gray-sheep effects by integrating social network structure into CF architectures [14], demographic and rating features can be combined to boost prediction accuracy on benchmarks such as MovieLens [15], and deep-learning models that infer ratings from textual item reviews extend item–item CF beyond explicit ratings alone [17].

Beyond user–item recommendation in generic e-commerce, specialized designs explore domain constraints and objectives. For educational video platforms, sustainable design principles and richer modeling of user context can trade off slight losses in standard precision/recall for gains in diversity and alignment with complex learning goals [16]. At the algorithmic level, more advanced clustering and bio-inspired optimization have been proposed to improve CF-based recommenders, for example by using swarm-intelligence clustering ensembles to refine user neighborhoods and improve Recall, Precision, MAE, and RMSE over standard baselines [18]. Our work situates hypergraph community detection within this broader space of structure-aware and hybrid recommenders, asking whether the additional higher-order modeling pays off relative to such strong but simpler alternatives.

3. Experiments

3.1. Data and Preprocessing

First-party logs from our VOD platform containing implicit feedback and item metadata were used. Each event record includes a user identifier, item identifier, timestamp, watch time, view count, and like/dislikes (plus other counters not directly used in the baseline MF models). Items carry content metadata (e.g., genres, characters, and tags). Then, the rows with missing user/item IDs and coerce timestamps to date times. Users and items were treated as strings (categories).

For each user, events were sorted by time and the last interaction was tested; all earlier interactions formed the training set. This “leave-one-last” protocol emphasizes next-item prediction and respects temporal order. Next, users were evaluated with ≥ 5 training interactions to ensure a meaningful history; others contributed to training, but not evaluation. For matrix factorization methods, the algorithm constructs a user–item CSR matrix with entries

$$r_{ui} = \log(1 + \text{watch_time}_{ui}), \quad (2)$$

Equation 2 is an implicit-feedback matrix $R \in \mathbb{R}^{|U| \times |I|}$ where U and I are the user and item sets, u indexes users, i indexes items, r_{ui} is the implicit feedback strength, and watch_time_{ui} is watch time in seconds. The “+1” avoids $\log(0)$. Unobserved pairs are treated as zeros in the sparse matrix.

Equation (1) is used by WMF^a; BPR^b uses a binarized version. Leaving the non-observed entries missing. Maintain (user, item) index maps to translate IDs and matrix

^a Weighted (Regularized) Matrix Factorization

^b Bayesian Personalized Ranking

^c Number of non-zeros

positions. The candidate set is the set of items present in the metadata table, and the methods may be recommended only within this catalog.

3.2. *Methods*

We compared six recommenders implemented as lightweight adapters around common libraries and our internal manager.

- Content TFIDF (Content Baseline). Content-based model from production service. It builds TF-IDF item vectors over metadata text, caches them once, and returns the manager’s top N recommendations per user.
- Two-tower (Content + History). A two-tower architecture: User embedding is a time-decayed weighted average of the TF-IDF vectors of items previously consumed by the user. Then, we used the manager’s class two-scale decay, combining a short and a long half-life via parameter α , which are cosine similarities between the user vector and all item vectors; consumed items were filtered out.
- MF-WMF-Cornac (Implicit ALS). The confidence-weighted MF was trained with Cornac’s WMF. Before training, we compacted the UI matrix to active users/items (rows/columns with ≥ 1 nnz^e). Multiple constructor signatures were tried to match Cornac’s version and then trained for a fixed number of iterations.
- MF-BPR-Cornac. Pairwise Bayesian Personalized Ranking trained using Cornac’s BPR on a binarized (observed=1) compacted UI matrix. Again, we tried multiple recognized argument names to ensure compatibility.
- Graph Communities (Louvain / Leiden). Built an item-item co-watch graph from training events:
 - Count unique co-occurrences per user, then optionally normalize by Jaccard

$$\omega(a, b) = \frac{co(a,b)}{|U(a)|+|U(b)|-co(a,b)} \quad (3)$$

where a and b denote items and $U(a)$ is the set of unique users who interact with item a . Defining $co(a,b)$ as their co-watch count. Equation (3) defines the Jaccard-style edge weight, which is used to normalize the raw co-occurrence.

- Prune edges by min-edge weight, prune nodes by min-weighted degree, and cap neighbors to the top-K per node.
- Running Louvain and Leiden with a resolution parameter, merged tiny communities into their strongest neighboring communities.
- Recommend by selecting the user’s top communities (by frequency in history), forming a candidate pool, expanding with high-weight neighbors, and ranking by weighted degree within the pool.
- Hypergraph h-Louvain. constructed a hypergraph with item nodes and (i) item–tag edges and (ii) user-session hyperedges over {user, items seen}. Then, Louvain partitioning is run; recommendations are community-aware and scored by the sum of edge weights to the user’s seed items (personalized “seed_sum”) and weighted degree within the candidate community.

3.3. Evaluation

For each evaluation user, recommended up to $K=100$ items given the training history; the test target is the user’s last held-out item. Analyzed metrics:

- Recall@K. Fraction of held-out items appearing in the top-K list.
- nDCG@K. Discounted cumulative gain normalized by ideal gain. With one held-out item per user, this emphasizes a higher rank within the top K.
- Catalog coverage. Fraction of distinct catalog items that appear at least once across all user recommendation lists.
- Training time per method (milliseconds).
- Timing per user latency (ms) for model to generate a recommendation list.

Some methods may return fewer than K items if the candidate pool is small after filtering and pruning. We evaluate whether the method returns (no popularity padding) to reflect native behavior. In addition, we computed the share of test items that appear at least once in training to contextualize the achievable recall under a leave-last split. If there are more than sample-eligible users, we evaluate a uniform random subset with a fixed random number generator seed.

4. Results

With $K=100$, the content-based baseline clearly dominates. As shown in Table 1, Content-TFIDF attains the highest recall (0.243) and the strongest nDCG (0.072), indicating not only that it finds the most held-out items within the top-100, but also that its correct hits appear comparatively high in the list. In contrast, the collaborative factorization models and community-based methods cluster together well below the content baseline. The hypergraph variant and both MF models each reach recall around 0.081, but the hypergraph’s nDCG exceeds MF-WMF and MF-BPR, suggesting its few hits are ranked nearer the top, likely due to the seed-personalized scoring. The two-tower lags further on recall yet posts a middling nDCG, consistent with a representation that is reasonable for ordering near-neighbors but that lacks the breadth to surface many of the held-out items.

TABLE I. EVALUATION ON VOD DATASET ($K=100$).

Method	Training Cost		Inference Cost		Accuracy@100		Catalog Coverage		Community Structure	
	Train (ms)	Per-user (ms)	Recall@100	NDCG@100	Coverage	$n_communities$	Avg. comm. size	Modularity Q		
Content-TFIDF	524.37	414.951	0.2432	0.0722	0.8073	—	—	—		
Hgraph-hLouvain	256.93	0.283	0.0811	0.0502	0.2530	63.0	29.52381	0.4593		
MF-WMF	2894.26	0.080	0.0811	0.0291	0.1306	—	—	—		
MF-BPR	83.28	0.087	0.0811	0.0176	0.1096	—	—	—		
TwoTower	289.92	7.184	0.0541	0.0441	0.7991	—	—	—		
Graph-Louvain	38.08	0.389	0.0270	0.0053	0.0968	14.0	17.0	0.751817		
Graph-Leiden	25.79	0.387	0.0270	0.0053	0.0968	9.0	26.44444	0.726506		

Pure graph communities fare the worst, as recommended. Louvain and Leiden partitions show very high modularity, but this structural quality does not translate into ranking quality; recall falls to 0.027 with nDCG nearly flat. The partitions appear too coarse for retrieval at this sparsity level, trimming the cross-community edges that would otherwise be surface candidates for many users. The hypergraph’s 2-section produces many more, smaller communities (63 on average size ~ 29.5 , modularity ≈ 0.46), which, combined with personalized seed-sum scoring, helps nDCG relative to MF, but still does not approach the content baseline.

Fig. 1. Ranking quality (a) NDCG@k bars; (b) Recall@k bars. Content-TFIDF dominates both nDCG and recall; h-Louvain beats MF on nDCG at a similar recall, consistent with seed-personalized ordering.

Fig. 2. (a) Catalog coverage bars, (b) Community modularity Q . Content-TFIDF and Two-Tower expose $\sim 80\%$ of the catalog; graph methods cover $< 10\%$. A High Q for Louvain/Leiden does not translate to ranking gains.

The efficiency indicates a different story. Scoring for MF is extremely fast and the hypergraph method is lightweight, with graph methods close behind. The two-tower is modest, whereas Content-TFIDF is by far the slowest at query time because it requires global similarity operations against a large item matrix. The training cost is the heaviest for the WMF, but otherwise moderate for the other models. In short, the content model buys accuracy with latency, whereas MF and the hypergraph trade accuracy for speed. Coverage mirrors these patterns. Content-TFIDF and the two-tower expose most of the catalog within their top- k , whereas the hypergraph and MF cover substantially less, and the graph methods cover the least. The broader reach of content-driven approaches is consistent with their ability to score items using metadata, even when direct evidence of interaction is scarce.

Fig. 3. Efficiency trade-offs: (a) Per-user latency vs. Recall@k (log-x), (b) train time vs. Recall@k. MF and h-Louvain are ultra-cheap online (<1 ms) but trail in recall. Content-TFIDF buys accuracy at ~415 ms per query.

A salient ceiling in this dataset is that only approximately 71.4% of held-out items appear at least once during training. Any method that depends purely on historical co-occurrence—MF and graph/communities in particular—faces an inherent cold-start gap for approximately 28.6% of the targets. The content model is not bound by this constraint, since metadata can lift unseen or rare items into the ranking; this largely explains its recall advantage at $K=100$.

Fig 4. Pareto view, normalized radar (Recall, nDCG, coverage). Content dominates the accuracy–coverage frontier; h-Louvain sits mid-nDCG with weaker coverage; MF is better than graphs but not competitive with content.

4.1. Public Benchmark: MovieLens-1M

To test whether our observations generalize beyond a proprietary VOD platform, we replicated a subset of experiments on the public MovieLens-1M benchmark. Following common practice for implicit-feedback studies, we transformed ratings ≥ 4 into positive signals, performed a user-wise train/test split, and evaluated top- k ranking with $\text{Recall}@k$ and $\text{nDCG}@k$ for $k = 10, 20$. We compared item–item collaborative filtering (CF), a simple content-based model over movie genres (CBF), a rank-fusion hybrid CF+CBF, and the same community-aware methods used in the VOD setting: an item–item graph with Louvain communities and a hypergraph built from user hyperedges with Kumar clustering. The resulting ranking performance is summarized in Fig. 5.

Fig 5. MovieLens-1M ranking quality at $K = 10$. $\text{Recall}@10$ and $\text{nDCG}@10$ for item–item collaborative filtering (CF), content-based filtering over genres (CBF), a hybrid CF+CBF rank fusion, and community-aware models (graph communities with Louvain, hypergraph communities with Kumar). CF dominates, while graph and hypergraph communities slightly improve over weak CBF but do not surpass the CF baseline.

On MovieLens-1M, the strongest baseline is item–item CF: at $k = 10$ it achieves $\text{Recall}@10 \approx 0.14$ and $\text{nDCG}@10 \approx 0.25$, clearly outperforming both CBF and the CF+CBF hybrid. The genre-only CBF model performs poorly ($\text{Recall}@10 \approx 0.02$, $\text{nDCG}@10 \approx 0.03$), reflecting the limited expressiveness of coarse genre features relative to the rich text metadata available in our VOD setting. The simple hybrid improves over CBF but still trails pure CF in both recall and nDCG.

Community-based models again fall short of the best baseline. Graph-based communities with Louvain partitioning yield lower $\text{Recall}@10$ (≈ 0.09) and $\text{nDCG}@10$ (≈ 0.17) than item–item CF, despite reasonably high graph modularity ($Q \approx 0.085$) over a dense 3,212-node, 1.98M-edge item graph. Hypergraph communities via Kumar clustering attain higher hypergraph modularity ($q \approx 0.31$ with four item communities) and slightly

better ranking metrics than graph communities ($\text{Recall@10} \approx 0.10$, $\text{nDCG@10} \approx 0.18$), but still do not surpass the CF baseline. The corresponding community size distributions in the hypergraph and graph cases are shown in Figs. 6 (a) and (b) respectively, illustrating that MovieLens partitions are relatively coarse (few, large communities) even when modularity is non-trivial. In other words, the pattern observed on VOD repeats on MovieLens-1M: community detection—whether on graphs or hypergraphs—can improve over weak content baselines, yet fails to outperform strong, simpler CF models even when modularity is substantially higher. This reinforces our central claim that high structural modularity is neither necessary nor sufficient for top- k ranking quality, and that added higher-order complexity does not automatically translate into better recommendation performance on standard benchmarks.

Fig. 6. MovieLens-1M hypergraph community structures:

(a) Histogram of graph community sizes from Louvain partitioning of the item–item co-watch graph. The partition yields three large communities ($Q \approx 0.085$) over a dense 3,212-node, 1.98M-edge graph, illustrating that high modularity can coexist with coarse partitions that are insufficient for high recall at $K = 10$.

(b) Histogram of hypergraph community sizes obtained via Kumar clustering. The partition consists of four large item communities ($q \approx 0.31$), indicating relatively coarse higher-order structure despite moderate hypergraph modularity.

Error signatures were consistent across families. First, sparsity and pruning limit reach: minimum edge-weight thresholds, degree filters, and top- k neighbor capping simplify the co-watch graph but also sever weak yet useful bridges, which matters at large K . Second, MF often places correct items but too deep in the list, depressing nDCG. Third, while hypergraph communities help ordering around a user’s seeds, over-segmentation in a thin interaction regime restricts cross-community generalization and caps recall. Finally, the two-tower uses only TF-IDF features and hand-set time decay; without a learned re-ranker or richer features, it cannot close the gap to the production-grade content model.

Practically, the goal is maximum accuracy (while preserving speed), and the content baseline remains the right backbone in this setting. However, extreme online latency is the

primary constraint; MF or the hypergraph recommender provides inexpensive candidates, but they will require a downstream blender or re-ranker, ideally content-aware, to recover recall, especially for cold or tail items. If catalog exposure and diversity matter, content-based scoring already offers strong coverage; MF/graph methods require explicit diversification or popularity backfill to avoid concentrating on dense cores.

Fig. 5. Structure snapshot: (a) Item–item graph (Louvain) layout and, (b) hypergraph layout. Disconnected or weakly connected clusters illustrate why pure community partitions missed cross-community candidates at $K=100$.

These observations also suggest the following steps: On the graph and hypergraph side, relaxing pruning (lowering edge-weight and degree thresholds and raising the neighbor cap) and slightly increasing the community-resolution parameter could reduce over-segmentation and increase candidate reach at $K=100$. For the two-tower, tuning the short/long half-lives and the blend α , and mixing in popularity or category priors, should boost early-rank sharpness. For MF, modestly larger factor sizes and better confidence scaling aligned with watch-time distributions can improve ranking depth. Most promisingly, a lightweight hybrid—linearly blending content and MF/hypergraph scores with a weight fitted on a validation fold—should retain the content model’s cold-start strength while exploiting the latency advantages of learned collaborative signals.

5. Conclusion

We reassessed whether hypergraph community detection genuinely improves recommendation quality by incorporating higher-order structure, using both a real-world VOD platform and the public MovieLens-1M benchmark. In both settings, graph and hypergraph communities achieved high structural modularity, yet provided at best modest gains in top- k ranking and frequently underperformed strong, simpler baselines. On VOD, a content-driven TF-IDF backbone delivered the best Recall@100 and catalog coverage, while matrix factorization and hypergraph methods mainly offered latency advantages. On

MovieLens-1M, where item metadata is comparatively limited, item–item collaborative filtering became the dominant baseline; here again, graph and hypergraph communities improved over weak content-only models but failed to outperform plain CF, despite higher modularity scores.

Our analysis points to two main drivers: over-segmentation under sparsity, which limits cross-community recall, and noise amplification in heuristic higher-order links. These factors cause community partitions to prune weak but useful ties and to concentrate scoring within small clusters, capping recall even when local ordering is reasonable. In contrast, conventional content or CF backbones provide broader reach and better accuracy–coverage trade-offs. Taken together, these results argue for right-sizing complexity: keep content or CF models as the primary scorers, and use MF or hypergraph-based communities chiefly as fast candidate generators to be blended with content-aware signals. We further clarify when higher-order structure is more likely to pay off—namely, in regimes with denser, reliable multi-way context and verifiable relational signals. In our data regimes, however, the added algorithmic and implementation complexity of graph and hypergraph community detection did not justify its cost.

6. Discussion

Across both the proprietary VOD platform and the public MovieLens-1M benchmark, adding higher-order structure via graph or hypergraph communities did not consistently outperform strong baseline recommenders. In the VOD setting, adding higher-order structures via hypergraph communities did not beat a strong content baseline. The TF-IDF model achieved the best recall and nDCG, while the MF and community methods were faster but less accurate. On MovieLens-1M, where item metadata is limited to coarse genres, item–item collaborative filtering emerged as the strongest baseline, and the graph/hypergraph community methods again failed to surpass it, despite achieving non-trivial modularity scores. In both datasets, community-aware models tended to improve over weaker baselines (e.g., pure CBF with genres only) but fell short of the best-performing simple model (content on VOD, CF on MovieLens-1M).

Two mechanisms explain this gap. First, over-segmentation under sparse interactions improves local ordering around a user’s seeds but limits cross-community reach, which matters at larger K . Community detection, especially with pruning (edge weight thresholds, degree filters, top- k neighbors), tends to cut weak ties that often carry long-tail items into the top- k . Second, heuristic higher-order structure can amplify noise rather than signal: co-occurrence edges and hyperedges inferred from thin interaction data inflate connectivity in ways that are not predictive for recommendation. This is visible in both domains: hypergraph and graph partitions attain decent modularity, yet the resulting communities are either too coarse (graphs) or too fragmented (hypergraphs) to support strong recall.

For system design, this study argues for right-sizing complexity. On the VOD platform, a content-driven backbone (TF-IDF over richer metadata) offers the best accuracy and catalog coverage, while MF and hypergraph models mainly serve as ultra-fast candidate

generators. On MovieLens-1M, a simple item–item CF backbone is hard to beat; here, community-based models can be interpreted as structural refinements that add complexity without clear ranking benefit. A pragmatic architecture is to maintain a content- or CF-driven primary scorer and use MF or lightweight hypergraph scoring only as fast candidate generators paired with a content-aware or CF-aware blender/re-ranker. High modularity in graph partitions should not be read as ranking quality at large K ; weak ties pruned by community detection often enable recall, especially for tail and cold items.

Hypergraphs may still help when the multiway context is dense and reliable (e.g., session/group edges with verified semantics, curated tag ontologies, or multi-actor interactions) or when optimizing precision at very small K where local ordering dominates. In such regimes, higher-order structure can encode rich relational patterns that are hard to capture with simple pairwise graphs or factor models. Absent those conditions, however, the added complexity of hypergraph community detection—both algorithmic and engineering—does not justify its cost relative to strong, simpler baselines.

Our findings are still limited by data sparsity and by focusing on a single media domain (movies) across one proprietary VOD dataset and one public benchmark (MovieLens-1M). Future work should test curated or observational affinity/relational signals, richer multiway contexts (session/group edges with verified semantics), and learned blending/re-ranking that combines content with collaborative/hypergraph candidates. It is also worth exploring lighter pruning, resolution tuning, and Leiden-style local moves for hypergraphs, plus calibration of confidence scaling for watch-time or rating-derived confidence distributions. Validating additional domains (e.g., music, e-commerce, news) and running stronger significance and ablation studies would further strengthen the external validity of our conclusions.

Ethics Approval

This study analyzed de-identified aggregate interaction logs from a VOD platform collected under the platform’s Terms of Service. No direct identifiers were accessed, no user contact or intervention occurred, and all analyses were conducted under internal data-governance policies. According to our institutional guidelines, this work does not constitute human subject research and is exempt from a formal ethics review.

Conflicts Of Interest

The authors have no competing financial interests to declare. The data provider played no role in the study design, analysis, interpretation, or decision to submit the manuscript.

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